

Original article

Assessment of social media usage and reproductive health seeking behaviour among students of tertiary institutions in Northeast, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Social media (SM) has become a significant source of health information, particularly among young people. However, its role in shaping sexual and reproductive health (SRH) seeking behaviours among tertiary institution students in Northeast Nigeria remains understudied. This study aimed to assess the knowledge, usage patterns, and barriers related to social media as a source of SRH information among tertiary institution students in Bauchi State, Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted among 407 students selected via multistage sampling from four tertiary institutions in Bauchi State. Data were collected using a pre-tested, semi-structured questionnaire and analysed using IBM SPSS version 20. Descriptive statistics test was employed. **Results:** The mean age of respondents was 23.6 ± 4.9 years, with 64.1% male and 35.9% female. Majority (83.2%) had good knowledge of social media for SRH information. The most sought SRH topics were: how to avoid sexually transmitted diseases (40.1%), general sex education (33.0%), and sexual hygiene (24.2%). Key reasons for using social media included: "it contains a lot of information" (37.8%) and "privacy" (28.9%). Major barriers were poor internet connectivity (39.5%) and high cost of access (37.2%). Suggested strategies included improved internet connectivity (45.4%) and reduced access costs (29.5%). **Conclusion:** Social media is a widely used and valued source of SRH information among students. However, barriers such as connectivity, cost, and digital literacy limit its optimal use. Institutional interventions, digital literacy programs, and improved infrastructure are recommended to enhance SM's role in SRH education.

Keywords: Health-seeking behaviour, Sexual and reproductive health, Social media, Students, Tertiary institutions

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Introduction

The pervasive integration of social media (SM) into daily life has fundamentally altered information-seeking paradigms, especially among adolescents and young adults under 45 years of age. ¹ Platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, X (formerly Twitter), and Instagram facilitate user-generated content, interactive dialogue, and access to diverse viewpoints, presenting a distinct shift from the one-way communication of traditional media. ² Within the healthcare domain, SM has emerged as a potent tool for health promotion, education, and peer support networks. It presents a unique avenue for disseminating accurate sexual and reproductive health (SRH) information, which is particularly

crucial for young populations who often encounter significant barriers—including stigma, cost, and lack of confidentiality—when attempting to access formal health services.³⁴ In Nigeria, young people contend with substantial SRH challenges, including high prevalence of sexually transmitted infections (STIs), unintended pregnancies, and limited availability of youth-friendly health services.⁵ University students, who frequently engage in risky sexual behaviours, are notably underserved in terms of comprehensive SRH knowledge and accessible care.⁶

Globally, the use of SM for obtaining health information is increasing among adolescents and young adults, driven by its perceived accessibility, anonymity, and interactive nature.⁷ In Nigeria, mobile phone penetration is high, with reports indicating that 73% of youth use at least one social networking site daily.⁸ However, in regions like Bauchi State, socio-cultural norms, religious influences, and systemic health infrastructure deficiencies further restrict access to reliable SRH information and services. Concurrently, concerns persist regarding the variable quality of online health information, the spread of misinformation, and issues of digital exclusion.⁹ Despite the widespread adoption of SM, there is a paucity of research exploring how tertiary students in Northeast Nigeria utilise these platforms for SRH information, the specific obstacles they encounter, and how this potential resource can be optimally leveraged for effective health promotion. This study seeks to address this gap.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Area

A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in Bauchi State, Nigeria, between April and November 2023. Bauchi State has 20 local government areas and an estimated population of 7.4 million.⁸ The state hosts 16 tertiary institutions, including universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education.

Study Population

The study population comprised undergraduate and postgraduate students from selected tertiary institutions. Critically ill or absent students were excluded.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The minimum sample size was calculated as 384 using the formula for single proportions, with a 52% prevalence of SM awareness from a previous study,⁹ a 95% confidence level, and a 5% margin of error. Adjusting for 10% non-response, a final sample of 423 was targeted.

A multistage sampling technique was employed:

Stage 1: Four institutions (25% of 16) were purposively selected. The selected institutions were Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University (ATBU), The Federal Polytechnic, State University Gadau, College of Education (COE), Kangare

Stage 2: Two faculties per institution were randomly selected using simple random sampling by balloting. The selected faculties were ATBU (Science and School of Education Technology). Polytechnic (Engineering and Management). Bauchi State University Gadau (BASUG) (Law and Management). College of Education (COE) (Vocational technical education and Languages).

Stage 3: One department per faculty was selected; the selected departments were ATBU- Vocational training education, VTE Polytechnic- Electrical and Electronic Engineering, EE

BASUG- Economics

COE- English/Social studies

Stage 4: Students were selected systematically from departmental lists. After determining the sampling interval, the first student was identified by selecting a number at random between one and the sample interval calculated. Subsequent students were then identified by adding the sample interval to the serial number of the first sampled student. If no eligible respondent is found in the sampled students, next student was then selected.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a pre-tested, semi-structured questionnaire adapted from prior studies. The tool covered: Socio-demographics, Knowledge of SM for SRH, SM usage patterns for SRH

Research assistants were trained, and ethical protocols were followed.

Data Analysis

Data were cleaned, coded, and analysed using IBM SPSS version 20. Descriptive statistics summarised the dependent and independent variables.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Bauchi State Research Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was secured from all participants. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout.

Results

Socio-Demographi Characteristics

Of 423 questionnaires distributed, 407 were fully completed (96.2% response rate). The mean age was 23.6 ± 4.9 years. Majority were male (64.1%), aged 15–24 years (68.3%), and enrolled in universities (46.4%) (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents (n=407)

Variable	Freq	Percent
Age Group (years)		
15-24	278	68.3
25-34	113	27.8
35-44	14	3.4
45-54	2	0.5
Sex		
Male	261	64.1
Female	146	35.9
Institution Types		
Universities	189	46.4
Polytechnic	145	35.6
College of Education	73	18.0

Knowledge of Social Media for SRH Information

Most of the respondents (83.2%) had good knowledge of using SM for SRH information, while 16.8% had poor knowledge (Table 2).

Table 2: Knowledge Level of Respondents

Knowledge Level	Frequency	Percentage
Good (6-10)	339	83.2
Poor (0-5)	68	16.8

SRH Information Sought via Social Media

The most frequently sought topics were: How to avoid STIs (40.1%), General sex education (33.0%), How to identify STI signs (28.0%), Sexual abuse prevention (25.1%), How to maintain sexual hygiene (24.2%), Abstinence from premarital sex (24.5%), Pregnancy prevention methods (21.2%), Effects of female genital mutilation (14.5%), Pornography (8.0%).

Reasons for Using Social Media for Sexual and Reproductive Health seeking behaviour

Top reasons included: It contains a lot of information (37.8%), privacy (28.9%), convenience

(23.0%), shyness to talk to adults (16.5%), parents are too strict (13.3%), no one else to go to (14.5%).

Barriers to Using Social Media for SRH

The key barriers identified were: Poor internet connectivity (39.5%), high cost of access (37.2%), parental restrictions (26.0%), limited device access (24.5%), ignorance of reliable SM sites (12.7%), and poor typing/ search skills (8.3%).

Suggested Improvement Strategies

Among the suggestions recommended by the respondents were improved internet connectivity (45.4%), reduced access costs (29.5%), information literacy training (30.4%), training in effective search skills (26.3%), increased device ownership (25.1%), enhanced computer skills (24.5%) and reduced parental restrictions (22.4%).

Table 3. Social media as a means of SRH information among respondents

Variables	Freq	Percent
Indicate the Reproductive Health Information you have looked up or would enquire on social media:		
How to abstain from premarital sex?		
Yes	83	24.5
No	256	75.5
How to avoid contracting STIs?		
Yes	136	40.1
No	203	59.9
How to identify signs of STIs?		
Yes	95	28.0
No	244	72.0
Health effects of female genital mutilation?		
Yes	49	14.5
No	290	85.5
Different methods of pregnancy prevention?		
Yes	72	21.2
No	267	78.8
Sexual abuse:		
Yes	85	25.1
No	254	74.9
How to maintain sexual hygiene:		
Yes	82	24.2
No	257	75.8
General sex education?		
Yes	112	33.0
No	227	67.0
Pornography display?		
Yes	27	8.0
No	312	92.0

Table 4. Social media as a source for sexual and reproductive health-seeking behaviour:

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Shy to talk to adults?		
Yes	56	16.5
No	283	83.5
Are parents too strict?		
Yes	45	13.3
No	294	86.7
Is social media private?		
Yes	115	28.9
No	224	66.1
Convenient to search social media?		
Yes	78	23.0
No	261	77.0
No one to go to?		
Yes	49	14.5
No	290	85.5
Contains a lot of information?		
Yes	128	37.8
No	211	62.2

Table 5. Barriers of Using Social Media on SRH seeking behaviour:

Variables	Freq	Percent
Parental restrictions:		
Yes	88	26.0
No	251	74.0
Poor social media connection:		
Yes	134	39.5
No	205	60.5
High cost of access tools:		
Yes	126	37.2
No	213	62.8
Limited access to phone/ipad/computer:		
Yes	83	24.5
No	256	75.5
Poor typing/search skills?		
Yes	28	8.3
No	311	91.7
Ignorance of good social media sites?		
Yes	43	12.7
No	296	87.3
Ignorant of RH seeking behavior?		
Yes	42	12.4
No	297	87.6

Table 6. Strategies to employ to enhance use of social media for RH information

Variables	Freq	Percent
Less parental restriction		
Yes	76	22.4
No	263	77.6
Improved social media connection?		
Yes	154	45.4
No	185	54.6
Reduction in social media access cost?		
Yes	100	29.5
No	239	70.5
Ownership of phone/iPad/computer?		
Yes	85	25.1
No	254	74.9
Enhanced computer skills?		
Yes	83	24.5
No	255	75.2
Improved social media search skills?		
Yes	89	26.3
No	250	73.7
Acquisition of information literacy skills?		
Yes	103	30.4
No	236	69.6

Discussion

This study reveals that social media is a prevalent and valued source of SRH information among tertiary students in Bauchi State, consistent with trends in many settings.¹⁰ The high level of SM knowledge (83.2%) contrasts with some Nigerian studies on the knowledge of sexual reproductive health, which reported almost similar awareness, suggesting regional or institutional variations.¹¹ Students primarily sought information on STI prevention, general sex education, and sexual hygiene – indicating a strong interest in preventive and educational content. This aligns with findings from Nepal, where adolescents frequently searched for condom use information online⁹. However, topics like pregnancy prevention and female circumcision were less frequently sought, possibly due to cultural sensitivities or prior knowledge. Privacy and information abundance were key motivators for SM use, supporting the "uses and gratifications" theory. This reflects SM's role as a confidential and resource-rich platform for sensitive health topics, especially in conservative settings.

Barriers such as poor connectivity, high costs, and limited digital skills mirror challenges reported in other low-resource contexts.¹² These barriers underscore the digital divide and highlight the need for infrastructural and educational interventions.

Recommended strategies—improved connectivity, cost reduction, and digital literacy training—a pragmatic and align with national digital health objectives. Institutions should integrate SM-based SRH education into existing curricula and provide safe, moderated platforms for student engagement

Limitations

- Self-reported data may be subject to social desirability bias.
- The cross-sectional design limits causal inference
- Findings may not be generalizable to non-student youth or other regions.

Conclusion

Social media serves as a significant and accepted channel for SRH information among tertiary students in Bauchi State. While students demonstrate proactive online health-seeking behaviours, structural and skill-based barriers impede their full potential. Targeted interventions focusing on improving access, affordability, and digital literacy are essential to harness SM's capacity for enhancing SRH education and outcomes

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **Institutional Actions:**
Integrate digital literacy and SRH education into orientation programs.
Establish moderated, confidential SM platforms (e.g., WhatsApp groups, Facebook pages) for SRH Q&A.
2. **Policy Interventions:**
Collaborate with telecom providers to offer subsidized data plans for educational and health content.
Strengthen regulations to combat SRH misinformation on SM.
3. **Programmatic Strategies:**
Develop SM-based SRH campaigns focusing on STI prevention, contraception, and consent.
Train peer educators to provide accurate SRH information via SM.
4. **Research and Development:**
Conduct longitudinal studies to assess SM's long-term impact on SRH behaviours.

Explore the potential of AI and chatbots for scalable SRH counselling.

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